

A WELL-ORGANIZED VLSI STRUCTURE OF MEDIAN FILTER USING 8 BIT DATA COMPARATOR

G.Lakshmi Vara Prasad^{1*} N.suresh² R.Venkatesan³ R.Venkatesan³ V. Jai Kumar⁴ A.Arun chakravarthy⁵
^{1,2,3,5}Department of Information Technology, QIS College of Engineering and Technology, Ongole,
India

⁴Department of ECE, QIS College of Engineering and Technology, Ongole, India

*Corresponding Author: G.Lakshmi Vara Prasad&gamidi.lakshmi@qiscet.edu.in

Abstract: Information mining, data sets, ATM and correspondence exchanging, logical registering, booking, man-made brainpower, advanced mechanics, picture, video, and flag handling all require arranging. The proposed work fosters a clever information comparator to monetarily sort/rank request networks by speed, power, and region. This study presents a region productive Middle Channel Comparator. This proposed framework was executed in Verilog HDL, mimicked by Model sim 6.4 c, and orchestrated by Xilinx. FPGA Austere 3 XC3S 200 TQ-144 executes the proposed framework. Six 8-digit comparators are proposed. These six comparators were enhanced for XCV1000-4bg560 utilizing Xilinx 7.1i compiler instrument and VHDL. Convey pick rationale based information comparators fit decreased region applications. Bit-wise rationale based information comparators were quicker. Double to-overabundance one information converters utilize less power. Low-power executions use twos supplement. Information comparators utilized equal and pipelined adjusted shear arranging engineering.

1. INTRODUCTION

Comparator networks in software engineering are unique gadgets with a decent number of wires conveying values and comparator modules that join sets of wires and trade values on the off chance that they are not in the suitable succession. Arranging networks are intended to sort fixed quantities of values. Arranging networks can't deal with randomly enormous sources of info and have a foreordained series of examinations paying little heed to past outcomes. Equal execution and equipment execution benefit from examination grouping autonomy.

Arranging networks are basic, yet their hypothesis is rich and unpredictable. Armstrong, Nelson, and O'Connor investigated arranging networks in 1954 and protected the strategy. Equipment or programming can execute arranging

organizations. Parallel number comparators can be worked as basic three-state electronic gadgets, as indicated by Donald Knuth. Batcher prescribed using them to construct PC equipment exchanging networks in 1968, supplanting transports and crossbar switches. Arranging nets, explicitly bitonic blend sort, have been utilized by the GPGPU people group to fabricate arranging calculations for designs handling units since the 2000s.

2. Related Work

CAS block cost and number decide equipment cost and power use. "Exceptionally Enormous Scope Reconciliation" is VLSI. This field packs more rationale gadgets into more modest spaces. VLSI can fit board-sized hardware into a couple of millimeters! This has empowered already impossible accomplishments. VLSI is all over the

place. Your PC, car, cell, and different gadgets. This requires a ton of expertise in a few region of similar subject, which we will examine later. Power utilization diminishes when a chip replaces a few conventional parts. Decreasing power use permits a more modest, less expensive power supply, less intensity.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM TECHNIQUE:

The Conventional binary design is having the following disadvantages

- Less compact
- High Cost
- Less Accuracy

4. PROPOSED METHOD:

The Proposed Information Comparator has two data sources and results. Information comparators have rationale circuits that create a sign that drives two multiplexers to yield a high or low worth relying upon which information is higher. Fig. shows the information comparators' block outline. Comparators take away numbers.

Fig. 1: CAS Block

PROPOSED SYSTEM BLOCK DIAGRAM:

Fig 1(a): Application of Unary Design: Median Filter

Fig. 2: CAS network for a 3×3 median filter

PROPOSED SYSTEM FLOW:

Process flow of **RGB to binary image conversion (MATLAB Part)**

Fig. 3: RGB to binary image conversion

VLSI PART (USING Modalism)

Fig. 4: VLSI PART

Fig. 5: VLSI PART

MATLAB PART:

5. RESULTS

Snapshot is every application instant. It clarifies application. It will help the new user move forward.

Fig. 6: CONVENTIONAL BINARY DESIGN

Fig. 7: PROPOSED SHEAR SORTING BASED MEDIAN FILTER:

implementations, this method saves more than area and electricity.

REFERENCES

Fig. 8: OVERALL OUTPUT

6. CONCLUSION

Batcher sorting networks have several applications. Signal processing and communication switching networks like their regular structure. Given the enormous number of CAS units in a large sorting network, a standard weighted binary-based approach is expensive. Resolution raises VLSI cost. Such networks are limited by high hardware costs and power consumption. This research presents a space- and power-efficient unary-processing sorting network. The basic processing circuitry uses simple gates regardless of data resolution. The sole expense is translating data from/to binary. Compared to weighted binary

1. Karpagaabirami. S,P. Ramamoorthy, “ An Efficient VLSI Architecture for Removal of Impulse Noise in Images”, International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing, Vol. 3, Issue. 5, pp 567 – 574, May 2014.
2. Aayisa Banu S, Ms. Divya R, Mr. Ramesh .K, “Design and Simulation of Low Power and High Speed Comparator using VLSI Technique”, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, Vol. 6, Issue. 1, pp 119 – 122, January 2017.
3. Bharat H. Nagpara, Godhakiya Santosh M, Nagar Jay V, “Design and Implementation of Different types of Comparator”, International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research , Vol. 4, Issue. 5, pp 1321-1324 , May 2015.
4. Mehmood ul Hassan, Rajesh Mehra, “ Design Analysis of 1-bit CMOS comparator”, Proceedings of International Journal of Scientific Research Engineering & Technology, Vol. , Issue. , pp 68 – 72, 14-15 March 2015
5. K.Vasanth, S.Karthik, S.Nirmal raj, Preetha mol. P, “FPGA implementation of optimized sorting networks for median filter”, International Conference on robotics and automation, INTERACT 2010, Sathyabama university, Tamilnadu, India, pages 253-258, 2010.
6. Keping CHAN, “ Bit-Serial Realizations of a Class of Nonlinear Filters Based on Positive Boolean Functions” , IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems, Vol 36,no 6,pp 785-795, JUNE 1989.
7. Vasanth.k, Kavirajan A.A.F, Ravi.T, NirmalRaj.S, “ A Novel 8 bit digital comparator for 3x3 fixed kernel based modified shear sorting”, Indian journal of science and technology, vol 7, issue 4, pp 452-462, April 2014.
8. K.Vasanth, V Elanangai, S Saravanan, G Nagarajan, “FSM-Based VLSI Architecture for the 3× 3 Window-Based DBUTMPF Algorithm”, Proceedings of the International Conference on Soft Computing Systems:

- ICSCS 2015, Springer, Vol no 2, pp 234- 245, 2015.
9. K.Vasanth, "VLSI Architecture of Decision based Modified Selection sort filter for Salt and pepper noise removal", International Journal on Intelligent Electronic System, Vol 13,no.4, Pages 41-56, August 2014.
 10. K.Vasanth and S.Karthik, "FPGA implementation of modified decomposition filter", International Conference on Signal and image processing, ICSIP 2010, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India, pages 526-530.
 11. Keshab K. Parhi, "Low-energy CSMT carry generators and binary adders", IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems, volume 21, issue 4, pp791, april 2013.
 12. S. Kale and R.S. Gamad, " Design of a CMOS Comparator for Lo w Power and High Speed", International Journal of Electronic Engineering Research, pp. 29–34, Volume 2 Number 1 (2010).
 13. Sunghyun Park and Michael P. Flynn, 2006, "A Regenerative Comparator Structure With Integrated Inductors ", IEEE Transactions on circuits and systems -I: Regular papers , Vol. 53, No. 8, Aug. 2006.
 14. X. Li, W. L. Kuo, Y. Lu, R. Krithivas an, T. Chen, J. D. Cressler, and A.J. Joseph, 2005, " A 7-bit, 18 GHz SiGe HBT Comparator for Medium Resolution A/D Conversion", IEEE 2005.
 15. Vishnu B. Kulkarn i, " Low-Voltage CMOS Comparators with Programmable Hysteresis is , New Mexico State University , New Mexico.
 16. R. Jacob Ba ker, "CMOS Circuit Design, Layout, and Simulation", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Second edition, 2005.
 17. Wu Rong, Wu Xiaobo and Yan Xiaolang, "A Dynamic CMOS Comparator with High Precision and Resolution", pp 1567- 1570, IEEE, 2004.
 18. R. Wang, Kaihang Li, J. Zhang, Bin Nie, "A High Speed High Resolution Latch Comparator for-pipeline ADC" , pp 28-31, IEEE, 2007.
 19. Meena Pancho re and R. S. Ga mad, " Low Power and High Speed CMOS Comparator Design Using 0.18 μ m Technology", International Journal of Electronic Engineering Research ISSN 0975 - 6450 Volume 2 Number 1 (2010) pp. 71–77 © Research India Publications .
 20. K. Vleugels , S. Rabii and B. A. Wooky, 2001, " A 2.5 V Broad band multi bit $\Sigma\Delta$ modulator with 95 db dynamic range", Digest of Technical Papers ,Feb.2001
 21. B. Razavi and B. A. Wooley, " Design Techniques for High -s peed, High- Resolution Comparators ", IEEE Journal of solid state circuits , Vol. 27, No. 12,Dec. 1992
 22. Ibrahim, Mr S. Jafar Ali, K. Singaraj, P. Jebaroopan, and S. A. Sheikfareed. "Android Based Robot for Industrial Application." *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology* 3, no. 3 (2014).
 23. Thangamani, M., and S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim. "Ensemble Based Fuzzy with Particle Swarm Optimization Based Weighted Clustering (Efps0-Wc) and Gene Ontology for Microarray Gene Expression." *In Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Digital Medicine and Image Processing*, pp. 48-55. 2018. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3299852.3299866>
B. Karthikeyan, K. Alhaf Malik, D. Bujji Babbu, K. Nithya, S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim, N. S. Kalyan Chakravarthy (2021) "Survey of Cooperative Routing Algorithms in Wireless Sensor Networks", *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, pp. 5316-5320. Available at: <https://www.annalsofrscb.ro/index.php/journal/article/view/702>
 24. Divya. R and Dr.R. Chinnaiyan, "Reliable Constrained Application Protocol to Sense and Avoid attacks in WSN for IoT Devices," 2019 *International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES)*, Coimbatore, India, 2019, pp. 1898-1901
 25. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan , M.S.Nidhya (2018), " Reliability Evaluation of Wireless Sensor Networks using EERN Algorithm" , Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Springer International conference on Computer Networks and Inventive Communication Technologies (ICCNCT - 2018), August 2018 (Online)
 26. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan , R.Divya (2018), " Reliable AI Based Smart Sensors for Managing Irrigation Resources in Agriculture" , Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Springer International conference on Computer Networks and Inventive Communication Technologies (ICCNCT - 2018), August 2018 (Online)
 27. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan , S.Balachandar (2018) , " Reliable Digital Twin for Connected Footballer" , Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Springer International conference on Computer Networks and Inventive Communication Technologies (ICCNCT - 2018), August 2018 (Online)
 28. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan , S.Balachandar (2018) , " Centralized Reliability and Security Management of Data in Internet of Things (IoT) with Rule Builder" , Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Springer International conference on Computer Networks and Inventive Communication Technologies (ICCNCT - 2018), August 2018 (Online)

29. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar (2017) “Reliability Assessment of Component Based Software Systems using Basis Path Testing” , IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems, ICICCS 2017, 512 – 517
30. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar(2017) ,”Construction of Estimated Level Based Balanced Binary Search Tree”, 2017 IEEE International Conference on Electronics,Communication, and Aerospace Technology (ICECA 2017), 344 - 348, 978-1-5090-5686-6.
31. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar(2017), Estimation of Optimal Path in Wireless Sensor Networks based on Adjacency List, 2017 IEEE International Conference on Telecommunication,Power Analysis and Computing Techniques (ICTPACT2017) ,6,7,8th April 2017,IEEE 978-1-5090-3381-2.
32. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, R.Divya (2017),” Reliability Evaluation of Wireless Sensor Networks”, IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems, ICICCS 2017, 847 – 852
33. Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Sabarmathi.G (2017),” Investigations on Big Data Features , Research Challenges and Applications”, IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems, ICICCS 2017, 782 – 786
34. Dr.S.Nirmala ,R.Chinnaiyan et.al. (2021). Blockchain based Secured Framework for Road Traffic Management using Fog Computing . International Journal of Computational Intelligence in Control 13(2)
35. G. Sabarmathi and Dr.R. Chinnaiyan, "Reliable Machine Learning Approach to Predict Patient Satisfaction for Optimal Decision Making and Quality Health Care," 2019 International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES), Coimbatore, India, 2019, pp. 1489-1493.
36. G. Sabarmathi and Dr.R. Chinnaiyan, “Big Data Analytics Framework for Opinion Mining of Patient Health Care Experience” International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC 2020), IEEE Xplore Digital Library
37. G. Sabarmathi and R. Chinnaiyan, "Reliable feature selection model for evaluating patient home health care services opinion mining systems," 2021 International Conference on Advancements in Electrical, Electronics, Communication, Computing and Automation (ICAECA), 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICAECA52838.2021.9675485.
38. G.Sabarmathi , Dr.R.Chinnaiyan (2018), “Envisagation and Analysis of Mosquito Borne Fevers – A Health Monitoring System by Envisagative Computing using Big Data Analytics” in ICCBI 2018 – Springer on 19.12.2018 to 20.12.2018 (Recommended for Scopus Indexed Publication IEEE Xplore digital library)
39. G.Sabarmathi , Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Reliable Data Mining Tasks and Techniques for Industrial Applications, IAETSD JOURNAL FOR ADVANCED RESEARCH IN APPLIED SCIENCES, VOLUME 4, ISSUE 7, DEC/2017,PP- 138-142, ISSN NO: 2394-8442
40. G.Sabarmathi, Dr.R.Chinnaiyan "Mining Patient Health Care Service Opinions for Hospital Recommendations" International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology 69.9(2021):161-167
41. Hari Pranav A; M. Latha; Ashwin. M. S; R. Chinnaiyan, "BlockchainAs a Service (BaaS) Framework for Government Funded Projects e-Tendering Process Administration and Quality Assurance using Smart Contracts," 2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI), 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICCCI50826.2021.9402348.
42. Hari Pranav A;M. Senthilmurugan;Pradyumna Rahul K;R. Chinnaiyan , "IoT and Machine Learning based Peer to Peer Platform for Crop Growth and Disease Monitoring System using Blockchain," 2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI), 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICCCI50826.2021.9402435.
43. M. Latha, M. Senthilmurugan and R. Chinnaiyan, "Brain Tumor Detection and Classification using Convolution Neural Network Models," 2021 International Conference on Advancements in Electrical, Electronics, Communication, Computing and Automation (ICAECA), 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICAECA52838.2021.9675585.
44. M. Senthilmurugan, M. Latha and R. Chinnaiyan, "Analysis and Prediction of Tuberculosis using Machine Learning Classifiers," 2021 International Conference on Advancements in Electrical, Electronics, Communication, Computing and Automation (ICAECA), 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICAECA52838.2021.9675482.
45. M. Swarnamugi & R. Chinnaiyan (2021). CNN based Vehicle Classification for Intelligent Transportation System in Unstructured Environments. International Journal of Computational Intelligence in Control 13(2)
46. M. Swarnamugi & R. Chinnaiyan (2021). CNN based Single-level and Multi-level Vehicle Classification Framework in Intelligent Transportation System. International Journal of Computational Intelligence in Control 13(2)

47. M.Swarnamugi , Dr.R.Chinnaiyan(2019) , Smart and Reliable Transport System based on Message Queing Telemetry Transport Protocol, ICICCS 2019 , 15-17 May 2019, Madurai. (Recommended for Publication Scopus indexed IEEE Xplore digital library)
48. Manoj Challa , Dr.R.Chinnaiyan (2019) "Optimized Machine Learning Approach for the Prediction Of Diabetes-Mellitus (Recommended for Scopus Indexed Publication in Springer - Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing Series)
49. Preetika B ; M. Latha; M. Senthilmurugan; R. Chinnaiyan, , "MRI Image based Brain Tumour Segmentation using Machine Learning Classifiers," *2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)*, 2021, pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1109/ICCCI50826.2021.9402508
50. Preetika B; R. Chinnaiyan, "An Open Source Distributed Virtualization for Enterprise Infrastructure using OVIRT," *2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)*, 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICCCI50826.2021.9402547.
51. R. Chinnaiyan and D. Stalin Alex, "Early Analysis and Prediction of Fetal Abnormalities Using Machine Learning Classifiers," *2021 2nd International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC)*, 2021, pp. 1764-1767, doi: 10.1109/ICOSEC51865.2021.9591828.
52. R. Chinnaiyan and S. Alex, "Machine Learning Approaches for Early Diagnosis and Prediction of Fetal Abnormalities," *2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)*, 2021, pp. 1-3, doi: 10.1109/ICCCI50826.2021.9402317.